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Factors Influencing Risk Management Practices among Poultry Layer Farm Owners in Bukidnon Province, Philippines

Rimar P. Francisco¹, Jesse Jay O. Villanueva^{2*}

^{1,2}Department of Animal Science, College of Agriculture, Mindanao State University-Main Campus, Marawi City, Lanao del Sur, Philippines

¹Corresponding Email: rimar.francisco@icloud.com

^{2*}Corresponding Email: jessejay.villanueva@gmail.com

¹ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1127-5263>

^{2*}ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2868-0760>

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Abstract.

This study examines the socio-demographic profile, risk factors, and management practices of poultry farmers, and explores their relationship with the growth and health conditions of layer chickens. The results indicate that the majority of respondents were middle-aged (40–59 years, 50%) and college graduates (46.7%), with poultry farming serving as their primary source of income (63.3%). Among the key concerns identified were financial risks, particularly high feed costs (mean = 3.23). Environmental risks, especially climate change (mean = 3.43), and health-related risks, such as mental stress (mean = 3.07), were also reported. In terms of production, poor laying performance ranked highest (mean = 3.40), while market risks were dominated by high commercial feed prices (mean = 3.33). Farmers strongly agreed with implementing risk management practices, including proper sanitation, vaccination, and biosecurity measures (overall mean = 3.47). However, statistical analysis showed no significant relationship between socio-demographic factors or perceived risks and the growth or health of the chickens ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that external factors such as environmental conditions and farm management systems may have a greater impact on flock performance than farmer characteristics or risk awareness.

Keywords: Farm Owners, Poultry Layer, Risk Factors, Risk Mitigation, Risk Management

1.0 Introduction

Poultry farms play a crucial role in global food production, supplying a significant portion of the world's meat and egg consumption (Wen, 2023). Poultry farming is one of the fastest-growing sectors in the livestock industry due to its relatively low production costs and high feed conversion efficiency compared to other livestock (Xu, 2021).

One of the major concerns in poultry farming is disease management. Studies highlight that poultry farms are highly susceptible to infectious diseases, which can spread rapidly and cause significant economic losses (Awawdeh, 2022). Risk determinants in poultry farming encompass a wide range of factors that influence the health, productivity, and sustainability of poultry operations. These determinants can be classified into biological, environmental, managerial, and economic factors, all of which play a significant role in determining the success or failure of poultry farms. Findings show that understanding these risk factors is crucial for disease prevention, operational efficiency, and ensuring food safety in the poultry industry (Osman *et al.*, 2021; Parry-Hanson Kunadu, 2020).

Risk determinants are essential for understanding the factors that contribute to the spread of diseases, environmental hazards, and economic vulnerabilities across various sectors, particularly in

agriculture and poultry farming (Pao *et al.*, 2022). These determinants can be categorized into biological, environmental, behavioral, socio-economic, occupational, economic, technological, and food safety factors, all of which interact to influence the likelihood and severity of risks. Identifying and assessing these determinants is crucial for mitigating potential threats, ensuring public safety, and promoting sustainable practices (Hashim *et al.*, 2023; Nwobodo *et al.*, 2022). Failure to address these risks can lead to severe consequences, including disease outbreaks, financial losses, and ecological damage. For instance, biological risk factors, such as pathogens that thrive in densely populated environments, significantly contribute to disease transmission in both animal and human populations (Boyce & Standley, 2019).

Understanding these risk determinants is essential for designing effective management strategies that strengthen the resilience of agricultural systems and protect public health. Accordingly, this study was conducted to identify the key factors influencing risk management practices among layer poultry farmers in selected poultry farms in Bukidnon Province.

2.0 Methodology

This section describes the research design, respondents, locale and setting, instruments, data-gathering procedures, fecal analysis, statistical tools, and the ethical considerations observed throughout the study.

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the socio-demographic profiles of layer poultry farmers, their knowledge and awareness of risk management, and the relationships between farmers' characteristics, their knowledge, and risk management determinants on layer poultry farms. Descriptive research allows for a clear portrayal of variables without manipulation, while correlational research identifies relationships among variables without establishing causal effects (SurveySparrow, 2023).

2.2 Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were layer poultry farmers in Bukidnon Province. The list of participants was obtained from the Provincial Agriculture Office, Municipal Agriculture Offices, and other relevant sources.

2.3 Research Locale and Setting

The study was conducted in Bukidnon Province and involved 30 respondents from six municipalities: eight (8) from Kalilangan, four (4) from Pangantucan, seven (7) from Maramag, five (5) from Valencia City, three (3) from Malaybalay City, and two (2) from Alae. Among the respondents, 19 were classified as small-scale poultry farmers, and 11 as semi-commercial. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), poultry farms are classified by flock size (PSA, 2022). This study focused specifically on layer poultry raisers within the area and was conducted from March to May 2025.

Bukidnon, shown in Figure 1, is a province in the northern region of Mindanao, Philippines. It is renowned for its extensive agricultural lands. According to the 2020 Census, the province had a population of approximately 1.54 million and covers a land area of about 10,498.59 square kilometers, making it one of the largest provinces in the country by area (PSA, 2021). The province is predominantly rural, with most residents engaged in agriculture, including poultry, crop, and livestock farming. Strategically located in central Mindanao, Bukidnon borders major cities, including Cagayan de Oro to the north and Davao City to the south.

Figure 1. Map of Bukidnon
<https://www.philatlas.com/mindanao/r10/bukidnon.html>

2.4 Research Instrument

In this study, data were collected using a self-prepared questionnaire administered to layer poultry farmers in Bukidnon Province. The questionnaire was structured into three sections. The first section addressed the socio-demographic profile of the participants, including age, educational attainment, and primary source of income. The second section focused on risk management factors relevant to poultry farming, including financial, environmental, health, production, and market risks. The third section examined the risk management practices farmers use to mitigate these risks. A Likert scale was used to quantify responses, employing a standard four-point format to measure the extent of agreement or frequency of practices (Masrom, 2016).

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The respondents were personally interviewed using a survey questionnaire. The data collected included their demographic profile, as well as information on financial, environmental, health, production, and market risks, along with the strategies used to mitigate them. Before completing the questionnaire, the respondents were given an overview of its contents. The responses were then consolidated, tabulated, and categorized by respondents' characteristics.

Fecal samples were collected from the experimental animals in the research area. Fresh feces were obtained as they were naturally excreted, then placed in labeled containers and stored in ice-chilled boxes to slow the development of nematode eggs during transportation. The samples were promptly delivered to the laboratory for analysis.

2.6 Fecal Analysis

Fecal analysis included assessment of morphological characteristics, including normal and abnormal feces, using the Bristol Stool Form Scale (Lewis & Heaton, 1997). Furthermore, in fecal analysis, direct smear methods were used to identify and count eggs and internal parasites, and quantitative techniques, specifically the McMaster Egg Counting Technique, were applied to examine the fecal samples (World Health Organization, 2008; University of Saskatchewan, 2021).

2.7 Data Analysis

Descriptive and correlational statistics were used to analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistics, including percentages, means, and standard deviations, were employed to summarize the socio-demographic characteristics of layer poultry owners and their awareness of risk management determinants. Percentages were used to express the relative magnitude of one quantity in relation to another, while weighted means assigned appropriate importance to each quantity being averaged. Standard deviation measures the dispersion of data points around the mean, providing insight into variability within the dataset (Artiza *et al.*, 2022). These descriptive measures offered a clear overview of patterns and distributions in the data (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2017).

The Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson's r) was used to examine linear relationships between continuous variables without implying causation (Field, 2018). This statistical test determined the strength and direction of relationships between demographic profiles and the growth and health of layer chickens, risk management practices and chicken performance, and risk mitigation strategies and poultry outcomes. Ranking was also applied to determine the relative position of items, assigning higher, lower, or equal ranks as appropriate (Artiza *et al.*, 2022).

2.8 Ethical Consideration

The study followed established academic ethical standards. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the research, assured of their right to withdraw at any time, and guaranteed the confidentiality of their responses. No identifying information was included in any reports or publications. The research procedures complied with the ethical guidelines of Mindanao State University–Main Campus and the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173).

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyzed data collected from respondents, along with statistical findings and relevant literature.

3.1 Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents. Among the poultry farmers, 50% were aged 40 to 59 years, indicating that the respondents were predominantly middle-aged. This was followed by 43.3% aged 25 to 39 years and 6.7% aged 60 years and above. Regarding educational attainment, 46.7% were college graduates, 30% had completed college up to the level (but not graduated), 13% were high-school graduates, and 10% had reached high-school level without graduating, showing that most respondents held college-level education or higher. Research indicates that higher levels of education among farmers are associated with improved agricultural practices and increased productivity (Paltasingh & Goyari, 2018). Regarding primary income source, 63.3% of respondents identified poultry farming as their main occupation, followed by business owners (20%), crop production (10%), and professional employment (6.7%). According to the 2020 report by the Philippine Statistics Authority, poultry farmers most often identify poultry farming as their main source of income (PSA, 2021).

3.2 Risk Factors

3.2.1 Financial Risk Factors

Table 2 presents the financial risk factors among layer-poultry farm owners in Bukidnon Province. The highest weighted mean was found for high-cost feeds (3.23), followed by inadequate management (2.87), high initial investment (2.87), and loss of capital (2.70). Debt or loans and interest rate each recorded a weighted mean of 2.63, movement in stock prices 2.60, new regulations 2.57, and the lowest values were for economic downturn and currency change (2.50).

The overall average for financial risks was 2.71, indicating that respondents generally agreed these were significant. More than half of the respondents agreed that high feed costs adversely affect production. This finding aligns with research showing that fluctuations in feed prices significantly impact the profitability of livestock production (Purdue Center for Commercial Agriculture, 2019).

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Variables	Frequency n=30	Percentage
Age		
25-39 years old	13	43.30
40-59 years old	15	50.00
60 years old and above	2	6.70
Mean		49
Highest Educational Attainment		
High School level	3	10.00
High School Graduate	4	13.30
College level	9	30.00
College Graduate	14	46.70
Primary Source of Income		
Business Owner	6	20.00
Crop Production	3	10.00
Poultry Farm	19	63.30
Professional Degree Holder	2	6.70

Table 2. Financial Risk Factors Affecting Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Financial Risk Factors	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Loss of Capital	5	11	14	0	2.70	Agree
2. Inadequate Management	3	20	7	0	2.87	Agree
3. Movement in Stock Prices	3	13	13	1	2.60	Agree
4. High Initial Investment	2	22	6	0	2.87	Agree
5. Depth or Loans	2	15	13	0	2.63	Agree
6. High Cost of Feeds	9	19	2	0	3.23	Agree
7. Economic Downturn	1	14	14	1	2.50	Agree
8. Interest Rates	4	11	15	0	2.63	Agree
9. Currency Changes	4	9	15	2	2.50	Agree
10. New Rules	3	11	16	0	2.57	Agree
Overall					2.71	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 - Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 - Disagree; 2.50-3.24 - Agree; 3.25-4.00 - Strongly Agree

3.2.2 Environmental Risk Factors

Table 3 presents the results of environmental risk factors among layer-poultry farm owners. Climate change had the highest weighted mean (3.43), followed by poor water quality (3.13), noise (3.10), and land use patterns (3.03). Water shortages received a weighted mean of 2.83, chemical pollution 2.53, loss of biodiversity 2.40, and alien species 2.37, with the lowest values for soil erosion and flooding (both 2.30), indicating that respondents generally disagreed that these were significant concerns. These results suggest that, among various environmental issues, climate change is perceived as the most critical.

Previous research indicates that climate change poses substantial challenges to animal agriculture, particularly poultry production, due to its impacts on heat stress, disease outbreaks, and feed availability (Nardone *et al.*, 2010).

Table 3. Environmental Risk Factors Affecting Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Environmental Risk Factors	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Land Use Patterns	1	29	0	0	3.03	Agree
2. Climate Change	14	15	1	0	3.43	Strongly Agree
3. Poor Water Quality	11	12	7	0	3.13	Agree
4. Noise	8	17	5	0	3.10	Agree
5. Chemical Pollution	4	9	16	1	2.53	Agree
6. Soil Erosion	1	8	20	1	2.30	Disagree
7. Water Shortages	6	14	9	1	2.83	Agree
8. Alien Species	1	12	14	3	2.37	Disagree
9. Flooding	2	7	19	2	2.30	Disagree
10. Loss of Biodiversity	2	10	16	2	2.40	Disagree
Overall					2.74	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 - Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 - Disagree; 2.50-3.24 - Agree; 3.25-4.00 - Strongly Agree

3.2.3 Health Risk Factors

Table 4 presents the results of health risk factors among layer-poultry farm owners. Health risks are considered a major concern in the poultry industry. Respondents agreed on several key health risks, including mental health stress (weighted mean = 3.07), exposure to poultry waste (3.03), lack of access to healthcare (3.00), and disease-causing microbes (2.93). Exposure to poultry dust and droppings, ammonia, both received a weighted mean of 2.80, followed by nutritional deficiencies and impacted crops (2.67), foodborne illness (2.63), parasites and infections (2.50), and infectious diseases from poultry (2.30). The overall average weighted mean for health risks was 2.77, indicating general agreement among respondents. These findings align with Donham *et al.* (2007), who emphasized that prolonged exposure to poor working conditions in confined animal feeding operations can lead to mental health issues such as anxiety and depression.

Table 4. Health Risk Factors Affecting Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Health Risk Factors	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Disease Causing Microbes	4	20	6	0	2.93	Agree
2. Lack of Access to Health Care	5	20	5	0	3.00	Agree
3. Infectious Disease from the Poultry	1	10	16	3	2.30	Disagree
4. Foodborne Illness	2	16	11	1	2.63	Agree
5. Nutritional Deficiencies and Impacted Crops	3	14	13	0	2.67	Agree
6. Poultry Dust and Droppings	2	20	8	0	2.80	Agree
7. Parasites and Infections	1	14	14	1	2.50	Agree
8. Ammonia Exposure	2	20	8	0	2.80	Agree
9. Poultry Waste Exposure	5	21	4	0	3.03	Agree
10. Mental Health Stress	7	18	5	0	3.07	Agree
Overall					2.77	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 - Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 - Disagree; 2.50-3.24 - Agree; 3.25-4.00 - Strongly Agree

3.2.4 Production Risk Factors

Table 5 presents the results of production risk factors among layer-poultry farm owners. Poor laying performance received the highest weighted mean of 3.40, followed by heat stress and flooding (3.13), poor feed quality (3.10), and poor management practices (3.07). Feed shortage scored 2.97, unpredictable poultry output 2.73, drug and vaccine failure 2.63, outbreak of disease and labor shortage both 2.53, and genetic issues received the lowest weighted mean of 2.43. The overall average weighted mean for production risks was 2.85, indicating general agreement among respondents. These results are consistent with Khan *et al.* (2020), who emphasized that poor laying performance is often linked to various stressors, including environmental conditions and management practices.

3.2.5 Market Risk Factors

Table 6 presents the results for market risk factors among layer-poultry farm owners. The high cost of commercial feeds received the highest weighted mean (3.33), indicating strong agreement among respondents, followed by transportation costs (3.23). High fluctuations in selling price and weather-related disruptions both scored 2.93; market instability and poor sales, 2.63; pest and disease outbreaks, 2.53; regulatory changes, 2.43; high disease incidence and export restrictions, both 2.40; and changing consumer preferences, the lowest weighted mean of 2.33, reflecting disagreement.

Table 5. Production Risk Factors Affecting Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Production Risk Factor	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Poor Laying Performance	14	14	2	0	3.40	Strongly Agree
2. Poor Management Practices	10	12	8	0	3.07	Agree
3. Outbreak of Disease	1	15	13	1	2.53	Agree
4. Drug and Vaccine Failure	5	9	16	0	2.63	Agree
5. Unpredictable Poultry Output	1	20	9	0	2.73	Agree
6. Heat Stress and Flooding	7	20	3	0	3.13	Agree
7. Poor Feed Quality	8	17	5	0	3.10	Agree
8. Feed Shortages	6	17	7	0	2.97	Agree
9. Genetic Issues	4	11	9	6	2.43	Disagree
10. Labor Shortages	2	15	10	3	2.53	Agree
Overall					2.85	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 - Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 - Disagree; 2.50-3.24 - Agree; 3.25-4.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 6. Market Risk Factors Affecting Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Market Risk Factors	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Market Instability and Poor Sales	2	16	11	1	2.63	Agree
2. High Cost of Commercial Feeds	11	18	1	0	3.33	Strongly Agree

Table 6 (continued). Market Risk Factors Affecting Layer Poultry Farm Owners

Market Risk Factors	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
3. High Fluctuation in Selling Price	2	24	4	0	2.93	Agree
4. High Disease Incidence	1	10	19	0	2.40	Disagree
5. Regulatory Changes	3	7	20	0	2.43	Disagree
6. Transportation Costs	7	23	0	0	3.23	Agree
7. Weather-Related Disruptions	5	18	7	0	2.93	Agree
8. Changing Consumer Preferences	1	8	21	0	2.33	Disagree
9. Export Restriction	3	8	17	2	2.40	Disagree
10. Pest and Disease Outbreaks	1	16	11	2	2.53	Agree
Overall					2.77	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 - Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 - Disagree; 2.50-3.24 - Agree; 3.25-4.00 - Strongly Agree

The overall weighted mean for market risk was 2.77, showing general agreement among respondents. These results indicate that the high cost of commercial feeds is the most significant market risk affecting production. Mason *et al.* (2016) emphasize that feed costs account for a substantial portion of total production expenses in poultry farming, often exceeding 60%. Addressing these market risks can help poultry raisers improve operational efficiency and better adapt to market challenges.

3.3 Risk Management Practices

Table 7 shows that the majority of respondents strongly agreed that maintaining clean, disinfected poultry facilities is essential, with a weighted mean of 3.60. Respondents also strongly agreed on other poultry management practices, including vaccination, strict adherence to protocols, and providing a nutritious diet with adequate water, each obtaining a weighted mean of 3.57. Proper waste management received a weighted mean of 3.50, while separating multi-age poultry, maintaining proper sanitation, isolating sick birds, administering medication, and cleaning equipment and tools each scored 3.47. Additional practices, such as identifying and treating sick birds and maintaining proper ventilation, received 3.43, monitoring for parasites scored 3.40, and recalling chicken feed items and monitoring/managing temperature each obtained 3.33. The overall average weighted mean was 3.47, indicating that respondents strongly agreed with these poultry management strategies.

These results suggest that respondents are not only aware of potential risks in poultry farming but are also prepared to manage them effectively. Established practices such as isolating sick birds, timely medication, and proper sanitation are likely contributing to mitigating health threats. Bardosh (2020) reported that farmers who implement strategies such as controlled farm access and proper waste disposal are better equipped to handle disease outbreaks, reducing their vulnerability. Additionally, Awawdeh (2022) emphasized the importance of implementing effective disease management strategies, including vaccination programs and biosecurity measures, to minimize risk in poultry operations.

3.4 Relationship Between Demographic Profile and the Growth and Health Conditions of Layer Chickens

Table 8 presents the statistical findings, indicating that there are no significant relationships between the demographic profiles of poultry farmers (age, educational attainment, and primary source of income) and the growth (average body weight) or health (mortality rate) of their layer chickens. These results suggest that although farmers actively implement risk management practices, these efforts may not directly influence flock body weight or mortality.

Other factors, such as farm size, breed, or environmental conditions, may play a more substantial role. The lack of strong correlations may also result from the consistently high adoption of best management practices across farms, which reduces variability. Sørensen (2011) highlights that flock health and productivity are shaped by a combination of biological, environmental, and managerial factors, and that outcomes cannot be predicted solely based on farmer characteristics or risk perceptions. This underscores the importance of integrated, data-driven approaches to poultry management.

Table 7. Risk Management Strategies of Poultry Layer Farm Owners

Risk Management Strategies	Frequency				Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
	4	3	2	1		
1. Vaccination	18	11	1	0	3.57	Strongly Agree
2. Identifying and Treating Sick	14	15	1	0	3.43	Strongly Agree
3. Separating Multiage of Poultry Birds	15	14	1	0	3.47	Strongly Agree
4. Proper Sanitation	15	14	1	0	3.47	Strongly Agree
5. Medication	15	14	1	0	3.47	Strongly Agree
6. Isolation of Sick Birds	15	14	1	0	3.47	Strongly Agree
7. Providing a Nutritious Diet and Plenty of Water	18	11	1	0	3.57	Strongly Agree
8. Poultry must be Clean and Disinfected	19	10	1	0	3.60	Strongly Agree
9. Recalling Chicken Food Items	11	18	1	0	3.33	Strongly Agree
10. Maintaining Proper Ventilation	14	15	1	0	3.43	Strongly Agree
11. Monitoring and Managing Temperature	11	18	1	0	3.33	Strongly Agree
12. Proper Waste Management	16	13	1	0	3.50	Strongly Agree
13. Cleaning Equipment and Tools	15	14	1	0	3.47	Strongly Agree
14. Monitoring for Parasites	13	16	1	0	3.40	Strongly Agree
15. Keeping a Strict Entry Protocol	18	11	1	0	3.57	Strongly Agree
Overall					3.47	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 - Strongly Disagree; 1.75-2.49 - Disagree; 2.50-3.24 - Agree; 3.25-4.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 8. Relationship between the Demographic Characteristics of Poultry Farmers and the Growth and Health Status of Layer Chickens

Characteristics	p-value	Interpretation
Age		
1. Age of Poultry Farmer and the Average Body mass of their chicken	0.248	Not Significant
2. Age of Poultry Farmers and the Mortality rate of their chicken	0.697	Not Significant
Educational Attainment		
1. Highest Educational Attainment of Poultry Farmers and the Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.259	Not Significant
2. Highest Educational Attainment of Poultry Farmers and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.559	Not Significant

Table 8 (continued). Relationship between the Demographic Characteristics of Poultry Farmers and the Growth and Health Status of Layer Chickens

Characteristics	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Primary Source of Income		
1. Primary Source of Income of Poultry Farmers and the Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.388	Not Significant
2. Primary Source of Income of Poultry Farmers and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.209	Not Significant

3.5 Relationship Between Risk Management and the Growth and Health of Layer Chickens

Table 9 presents the results, showing that there is no significant relationship between poultry farmers' perceptions of various risk factors, financial, environmental, health, production, and market risks, and the actual growth (average body weight) or health (mortality rate) of their layer chickens. All statistical tests produced *p*-values greater than 0.05, indicating that the level of concern or agreement with these risk factors does not significantly influence flock performance. This suggests that farmers' understanding and recognition of potential risks to poultry welfare do not directly translate into measurable differences in flock outcomes. Practical on-farm responses, specific management actions, and external factors, such as climate, disease exposure, and genetics, are likely more influential than risk perception alone. Alarcón et al. (2013) emphasize that risk awareness campaigns among farmers must be paired with actionable interventions to improve animal health outcomes effectively. Knowledge alone may not lead to enhanced performance without associated behavioral changes or access to necessary resources.

Table 9. Relationship between Risk Management Practices and the Growth and Health Status of Layer Chickens

Practices	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Financial Risk		
1. Level of Agreement of Poultry Farmers on Financial Risk Factors and Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.743	Not Significant
2. Level of Agreement of the Poultry Farmers on Financial Risk Factor and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.525	Not Significant
Environmental Risk		
1. Level of Agreement of Poultry Farmers on Environmental Risk Factors and Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.798	Not Significant
2. Level of Agreement of the Poultry Farmers on Environmental Risk Factor and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.617	Not Significant
Health Risk		
1. Level of Agreement of Poultry Farmers on Health Risk Factors and Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.334	Not Significant
2. Level of Agreement of the Poultry Farmers on Health Risk Factor and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.488	Not Significant
Production Risk		
1. Level of Agreement of Poultry Farmers on Production Risk Factors and Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.493	Not Significant

Table 9 (continued). Relationship between Risk Management Practices and the Growth and Health Status of Layer Chickens

Practices	p-value	Interpretation
2. Level of Agreement of the Poultry Farmers on Production Risk Factor and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.240	Not Significant
Market Risk		
1. Level of Agreement of Poultry Farmers on Market Risk Factors and Average Body Mass of their chicken	0.689	Not Significant
2. Level of Agreement of Poultry Farmers on Market Risk Factors and the Mortality Rate of their chicken	0.674	Not Significant

3.6 Relationship between Risk Mitigation Strategies and the Growth and Health Condition of the Layer Chicken

Table 10 shows that there is no significant relationship between poultry farmers’ level of agreement on ways to overcome risk and the average body mass ($p = 0.123$) or mortality rate ($p = 0.054$) of their chickens. Although the correlation with mortality rate approaches significance, it remains above the 0.05 threshold, leading to a failure to reject the null hypothesis in both cases. These findings suggest that while farmers may be aware of effective risk management strategies, this awareness does not necessarily translate into measurable improvements in flock performance. Tse *et al.* (2012) emphasize that knowing how to mitigate risk is insufficient on its own; the effectiveness of livestock production depends on the degree to which these measures are actually implemented. Targeted training and investments in resources are essential to convert knowledge into practice.

Table 10. Relationship Between Risk Mitigation Strategies and the Growth and Health of Layer Chickens

Strategies	p-value	Interpretation
Way to Overcome Risk		
1. Level of agreement of poultry farmers on ways to overcome risk and average body mass of their chicken	0.123	Not Significant
2. Level of agreement of poultry farmers on ways to overcome risk and mortality rate of their chicken	0.054	Not Significant

3.7 Stool Assessment

3.7.1 Morphology

Figure 2a and 2b show fecal samples collected and classified according to the Bristol Stool Chart (Lewis & Heaton, 1997). Among the 30 experimental samples, 28 were classified as type 4 or 5, indicating normal fecal consistency, while two were classified as type 7, indicating diarrhea. The predominance of normal stool types suggests that most of the chickens had stable digestive health at the time of sampling. Amar (2022) notes that normal poultry feces are firm, brownish, and well-formed, reflecting a healthy gastrointestinal status. In contrast, abnormal stools, such as watery or discolored feces, may indicate disease or dietary imbalance.

Figure 2A. Normal Type 5

Figure 2B. Diarrhea Type 7

3.7.2 Egg Count

Table 11 presents the presence and intensity of parasitic infections across multiple poultry farms. Egg counts were determined using the McMaster and Mini-FLOTAC techniques (Tagesu, 2018; Cringoli, Rinaldi, Maurelli, & Utzinger, 2017). In this study, egg counts were classified as follows: 0–200 eggs as normal, 201–500 eggs as moderate, and >501 eggs as high infection. Among the parasites detected, *Coccidia* had the highest and most widespread occurrence, affecting 17 farms, with egg counts ranging from 50 to 1,000 oocysts per 2 g of feces. The highest count of 1,000 oocysts was observed in Farm 8, indicating a potential outbreak-level infection. *Ascaridia* spp., a type of roundworm, was also notable, with Farm 19 reporting a high count of 650 eggs, classified as a heavy infection. Other parasites, including *Strongyloides* spp., Strongyloid eggs, and *Tetrameres* spp., were present in fewer farms but still raised concern, particularly Strongyloid eggs in Farm 6 (500 eggs), indicating a significant worm burden. *Coccidia* exhibited the highest egg counts among the parasites detected across farms. Wen (2023) indicated that high *Coccidia* egg counts in fecal samples indicate significant parasitic burdens that can adversely affect poultry health and productivity.

Figure 3a, b, and c shows parasites identified in poultry feces, including *Strongyloides* spp., Strongyloid eggs, *Coccidia* (*Eimeria* spp.), *Tetrameres* spp., and *Ascaridia* spp., all of which pose substantial health risks to flocks. *Strongyloides* spp. can cause gastrointestinal disturbances and increase overall parasite load, while Strongyloid eggs suggest potential gastrointestinal issues that reduce feed efficiency and growth. *Coccidia* cause coccidiosis, which results in diarrhea, weight loss, and decreased egg production, leading to economic losses. *Tetrameres* spp. Affect nutrient absorption, and *Ascaridia* spp. can cause intestinal blockages. Khan *et al.* (2020) emphasized that these parasites significantly reduce weight gain and feed efficiency in poultry. Effective monitoring, deworming, and biosecurity measures are essential to control these parasites and maintain flock health, highlighting the importance of proactive management strategies in poultry farming.

Table 11. Egg Counts Across Different Poultry Layer Farms

Characteristic	Egg Count	Classification
Strongyloides spp.		
Farm 3	150	Moderate Infection
Farm 5	100	Normal
Farm 7	50	Normal
Farm 9	100	Normal
Strongyloid eggs		
Farm 6	500	High Infection
Farm 10	200	Moderate Infection

Table 11 (continued). Egg Counts Across Different Poultry Layer Farms

Characteristic	Egg Count	Classification
Coccidia		
Farm 1	100	Normal
Farm 4	400	Moderate Infection
Farm 7	200	Moderate Infection
Farm 8	1,000	High Infection
Farm 10	350	Moderate Infection
Farm 13	100	Normal
Farm 14	150	Normal
Farm 15	150	Normal
Farm 19	550	High Infection
Farm 20	50	Normal
Farm 22	100	Normal
Farm 23	50	Normal
Farm 24	50	Normal
Farm 25	100	Normal
Farm 28	100	Normal
Farm 29	100	Normal
Farm 30	100	Normal
Tetrameres spp		
Farm 21	150	Normal
Ascaridia spp		
Farm 15	150	Normal
Farm 19	650	High Infection
Farm 20	150	Normal

Legend: 0-200 - Normal; 201- 500 - Moderate; 500-up - High Infection

Figure 3A. Strongylid eggs spp

Figure 2B. Coccidia

Figure 3C. Ascaridia

4.0 Conclusion

Poultry farmers in Bukidnon encounter a range of risks, with financial, environmental, and production challenges being the most significant. The strong implementation of best practices in sanitation, nutrition, and biosecurity has helped sustain stable flock health and growth. Farmers' demographic characteristics do not appear to affect the productivity or health of their chickens significantly. This suggests that external factors, such as farm environment, breed, and overall management, play a more critical role in flock performance.

5.0 Contribution of the Authors

Rimar P. Francisco: The author conducted data collection, analyzed the findings, and wrote the entire manuscript.

Jesse Jay O. Villanueva: The author conceptualized the study, developed the research instrument, and supervised the validation process with subject-matter experts.

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7.0 Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest concerning the publication of this study.

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